

The Conceptualization and Development of the Social Self Image / Brand Image Construct: A Confirmatory Data Analysis Approach

Dr. Ahmad Khaldi ¹

Department of Marketing, School of Business. Australian College of Kuwait. West Mishrif, Kuwait

Abstract

This research paper reviews various conceptualizations and perspectives on the nature of the self image, brand image, and the social self congruity as presented in the previous literature. The aim of this paper is to propose a global and situation-free measure of the social self congruity construct. Confirmatory data analysis revealed that the proposed measure is highly reliable and demonstrates high levels of content, criterion, predictive, and convergent validity.

Keywords: Self image, brand image, image congruence, confirmatory factor analysis, symbolic meaning, consumer behavior, social interaction.

1. Introduction

The most basic and powerful fact of consumer behaviour according to Belk (1988) is that individual's identity directly translates into consumption, and that consumption is capable of revealing identity. This congruence between consumer's self image and the image of the brand, product, or retail store has been used by many researchers to explain and predict different facets of consumer behaviour such as: product use, product ownership, brand attitude, purchase motivation, purchase intention, brand choice, brand adoption, store preference, and store loyalty (Sirgy 1982; Sirgy & Samli 1985; Claiborne & Sirgy 1990).

2. Self Image and the Social Self Concept

Solomon (2002) sees the self-concept as a reflection of the beliefs a person holds about his or her own attributes and how he or she evaluates these qualities. Each individual has an image of himself or herself as a person, with certain traits and ways of behaving (Schiffman & Kanuk 2000). Assael (1987) explained that this perception of one's self is based on two concepts: the actual self concept which reflects individuals' perception of who they think they are and the concept of the ideal self which reflects individuals' perception of who they would like to be.

The concept of social self was first mentioned by Smith (1992) when he replaced the previous image-based perception of the self by a more experience-related one. For Smith (1992) the empirical self is the concept most central to personal experience. He argued that the empirical self has three main divisions: the material self (one's body and possessions), the social self (the impression one conveys to others) and the spiritual self (one's inner or subjective being). This situational role oriented view of the construction of the social self was later confirmed by MacKinnon, and Heise (2010) who concluded that individuals' social self is developed from the accumulation and integration of particular role performances and identities constructed throughout their social experiences. In this sense, the attributes of the social self is derived from the perceptions of our own self image by other people.

This view led some researchers to name the social self image as the "the looking glass self" to confirm the idea that the self is shaped by the reflected opinions of others (Schenk & Holman 1980; Solomon 2002; Hood 2012) and that people shape their self image to fit other people's perceptions and expectations. Therefore, social self is a manifestation of a multifaceted images rather than a reflection of a fixed image because it is a reflection of our multiple images as seen by others in each social role or interaction that we experience. If we believe in this view, then we are a product of those around us, or at least, what we believe they expect from us as each person around us holds a looking glass image of us every time we interact and we present a different self (Hood 2012).

This conceptualization of the social self is really more comprehensive than most of the other self image constructs. According to Sirgy (1982), if the social self concept can be thought of as having different components, or role identities, (where only some of these are active at any given time), then the concept of social self can replace both the actual self-image as well as the ideal self-image concepts. The ramifications of the social self image are still evolving with the significant advancement of digital communities and online communication possibilities as Balick (2014) concluded in his research about the relation between the expression

¹The author wishes to thank his colleague Ms. Marcelle de la Roche for her continuance support and encouragement which made this paper see the light.

of the virtual self image online and the concept of social self offline. He explained that, depending on the feelings of being recognized or misrecognised by peers offline, individuals choose to present a false or true social self image on social networks. In a later study, Kang and Johnson (2015) also confirmed the importance of the social self image as one of the main factors that directly influence positive word of mouth behaviours for retail apps usage online.

3. The Nature of Brand Image and Self Congruence

Researchers considered brand image as a combination of the physical qualities of the product and the beliefs, attitudes and feelings that consumers attach to it (Levy 1978; Kotler 1988; Dobni & Zinkhan 1990). Other researchers adopted a more trait based conceptualization of brand image and viewed it as a set of personal image attributes or a set of associations organized in a meaningful way (Sirgy 1982; Aaker 1997). Contrary to the one-sided product-based view of brand image, Friedman (1986) emphasized that the psychological characteristics of both the user and the product must be taken into consideration in constructing brand image. In line with this later view, To (1994) concluded that brand image is audience specific, culture-bound, socially constructed. Such evolutionary view of the brand image construct was confirmed by Fournier (1995) who believed that the brand has its own personality as an active, partner in the relationship between the consumer and the brand.

From a more humanistic perspective, Allen & Olson (1995) considered brand personality as the specific set of meanings that describe the "inner" characteristics of a brand. Consumers construct these meanings according to perceived brand behaviours. This perception usually takes a narrative form when the brand is shown "doing things" in advertising. Therefore, narratives and dramas in advertising provide more opportunities for marketers to portray brand's intentional behaviours, which are the bases for personality inferences, according to Allen & Olson (1995).

A similar conceptualization was presented by Aaker (1997) who depended on the psychological qualities of the product in image construction. Aaker defined brand personality as the set of human characteristics associated with a brand. Aaker's view draws the attention to a very important fact regarding the nature of brand image. That is brand image should not only be considered by researchers as a mere reflection of the user image, rather, a brand can also acquire a distinct personality of its own as an active, partner in the relationship between the consumer and the brand, as Fournier (1995) previously explained.

Consumers' perception of brand image can lead them to feel more personal relevance to brands that are perceived to have similar traits to their own self image as Overstreet (1993) explained in an investigation of children's inferences based on brand personality. Overstreet proved that children make inferences about brand personality, make inferences about other children based on brand personality, and apply brand personality to themselves. Many early researchers (Gardner & Levy 1955; Tucker 1957; Schenk & Holman 1980; Johar & Sirgy 1991) also demonstrated that when consumers feel self-congruity with a brand, they will be motivated to purchase or use that brand to satisfy self-consistency needs. This opinion adopted the idea that consumers prefer brands whose images are congruent to their self images because these brands express consumers' self images to significant others. Another explanation was presented by the symbolic self-completion theory of Wicklund & Gollwitzer (1982) who proposed that individuals lacking the indicators of an aspired-to self definition will display other compensating indicators of the same self definition. The self symbolizing occurs when an individual feels "incomplete" in certain areas and compensates by using or displaying other products and symbols that are socially recognized as representing "completeness." In their research, Wicklund & Gollwitzer (1982) successfully predicted that MBA students who lacked certain indicators of business success (e.g., a high GPA, several job offers) would compensate by displaying other indicators of business success, such as expensive suits, watches, or brief cases.

The self completion theory can only apply when brands are conspicuously consumed as Sirgy, et al (1986) argued. They demonstrated that brand conspicuousness is positively correlated to brand self-expressiveness. They explained that socially visible brands associate with the characteristics of the user more than privately consumed brands. Consumers use product symbolism to define themselves in the context of a specific situation, according to Wright et. al. (1992), who also proposed that product conspicuousness and uniqueness enhance the recognition and learning of product symbols.

Grimm (1993) explained that the mere perception of brand image attribute, without self referencing is not enough to form consumer's brand preference, and that is exactly why, according to Grimm (1993), self congruence is a vital contributor to build brand preference. Therefore, the essential influence on brand preference comes from consumer's perception of self congruity, and not from the plain perception of brand image traits.

Researchers have also found that self congruency affects consumers' intentions to buy as well as the actual buying of goods and services. Kang (1996) indicated that the image congruency between the self and the typical participant in a given type of sport have a significant direct impact on intentions to begin the sports or exercise. Burroughs (1996) also proved that impulsive buying behaviour occurs when a match is recognized between the symbolic meanings of a particular product and consumer's self-concept. When consumers perceive

this congruence, their urge to purchase the item will override the analytical assessments of the purchasing situation, according to Burroughs (1996).

In a research by Sirgy et al (1997), it was concluded that self/brand image congruence is a highly valid predictor of other consumer variables including brand preference, preference for product form, satisfaction, brand attitude, and educational program choice. However, Quester et al (2000) noted that the validity of self congruity as a predictor differs according to the type of product, functional or status-related, and to the cultural background of respondents, collectivistic or individualistic. Self congruity was also demonstrated to be a vital predictor of online buying behaviours. Sixt (2013) explained that when consumers feel self congruity with a touristic destination image online, they are more likely to have a satisfying experience and share their experience on social media through consumer-generated content. In a later research, Khaldi (2014) also confirmed the existence of a positive effect of virtual/ideal self image congruence on consumers' enduring involvement in social media consumption (more specifically, on consumers' perception of the self expressive and hedonic values of social media consumption).

Finally, it is important to draw the attention that self congruity is not only a mere match or mismatch between the image of the self and the image of the brand, it is also a feeling of self relevancy to the symbolic value represented by the brand. Therefore, brand's self relevancy is achieved through consumer's ability to utilize the symbolic value of the brand for self expressiveness, and this would not happen unless the consumer perceives her/his self image and the brand's image to be congruent.

4. Self/Brand Image Congruence Measurement

The traditional measures of self/brand image congruity were used by many early researchers (Hughes & Naert 1970, Maheshwari 1974, Sirgy & Danes 1981, and Malhotra 1981). The traditional method of congruity measures is based on tapping the subject's perception of product-user image and the subject's perception of her/his own self-image along a predetermined set of image attributes (or traits) and adding the self-congruity scores across all image dimensions.

Sirgy et al (1997) explained that the traditional method of measuring self-image congruence is hindered by three key problems: (1) the use of discrepancy scores, (2) the possible use of irrelevant traits, and (3) the use of the compensatory decision rule. These problems, according to Sirgy et al (1997), are to some extent related to the multi-dimensionality and the piecemeal processing assumptions of the self congruity construct. Based on their analysis of the shortcomings of the traditional method of measuring self-image congruence, Sirgy et al (1997) designed a new direct and global measuring method which assumes that self-image congruence is a one-dimensional holistic perception process; therefore, the new method can overcome the problems associated with the traditional method.

Sirgy et al (1997) investigated the predictive validity of the two measurement methods of self-image congruence (the traditional versus the new method) in six studies involving different consumer populations, products, consumption settings, and dependent variables (brand preference, preference for product form, consumer satisfaction/dissatisfaction, brand attitude, and program choice). Sirgy et al (1997) explained that the new method is "based on tapping the psychological experience of self-congruity directly and globally" (P. 229). They used direct global scales (with high Alpha reliability indexes) to measure respondents actual self congruity across the researched products, brands, and services as Table 1 shows.

Table 1 The scale items for the new congruity measures in Sirgy et al (1997) study

Product, Brand, Or Service New Congruity Scale Items	Used in study..					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
[Using] this product is consistent with how I see myself	✓	✓				
[Using] this product reflects who I am	✓	✓	✓			
People similar to me use products like this	✓	✓	✓			
The kind of person who typically uses this product is very much like me [than other people].		✓	✓	✓		
This product is a mirror image of me		✓				
I can identify with those people who prefer this product				✓		✓
I am very much like the typical user of [or who prefer to use] this product.				✓		✓
The image of the typical user of this product is highly consistent with how I see myself				✓		
The image of the typical product user is very dissimilar from the kind of person I am						✓
I feel that my personal profile is similar to the typical product user						✓
I do not have anything in common with the typical product user *						✓
Please circle the number that best expresses how you see your self-image compared to the image of the typical product user (1= very dissimilar, 5= very similar)					✓	
I am not at all like any of the product users I know *						✓
Alpha reliability index	0.83	0.90	0.87	0.82	N/A	0.85
[] Words in brackets are omitted in some studies.						
* Reverse coded						

The results provided support for the high predictiveness of the new method over and beyond the traditional one. Sirgy et al (1997) reported the consistency of the findings across the investigated goods and services, different consumer populations and consumption settings. However, it should be noted that although Sirgy et al (1997) have developed a valid and reliable actual self congruity scale, they did not provide any measures for ideal self image congruity.

In a later study, Khaldi (2006) explained that the new method of measuring self congruity that is developed by Sirgy et al (1997) confines respondents to predetermined usage situations in their self congruity responses. Such confinement, according to Khaldi (2006), might suffer from the same drawbacks of forcing them to think in terms of a predetermined image dimensions in the traditional method. Furthermore, Khaldi (2006) explained that it would be very difficult for the researcher to encompass the effects of all usage situations that might occur. Therefore, Khaldi (2006) developed two situation-free scales to measure ideal self congruity and actual self congruity based on Sirgy et al (1997) direct and global tapping of the psychological experience of self-congruity. Both scales were demonstrated to be valid and reliable by Khaldi (2006) as shown in tables 2 and 3 respectively.

Table 2. Scale items for global measure of actual self/brand image congruence by Khaldi (2006)

	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neither agree nor disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly disagree</i>
Using XYZ Brand is similar to how I see myself.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
I am not like any of the typical XYZ Brand users.*	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
People similar to me use XYZ Brand .	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
The kind of person who typically uses XYZ Brand is much like me.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
I do not have much in common with the image of the XYZ Brand user.*	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
I see my self image as similar to the image of the typical user of the XYZ Brand	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
* Reverse coded					

Table 3 Scale items for global measure of ideal self/brand image congruence by Khaldi (2006)

	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neither agree nor disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly disagree</i>
Using XYZ Brand makes me feel highly of myself	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand completes the image of who I would like to be.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand reflects the kind of person I prefer to be.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand would help me to express a more positive image of myself.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
I may like myself better if I were to use XYZ Brand .	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
The image of the XYZ Brand user is consistent with the ideal image I want to reflect of myself.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand would make me feel more special than using other brands.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
People who use XYZ Brand are much like how I prefer to see myself.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
* Reverse coded					

Furthermore, Khaldi (2006) have also demonstrated a higher predictive validity of the new situation-free global method of measuring self congruity, over and beyond the traditional measures of self congruity.

5. Developing the Social Self/Brand image Congruence Scale

Building on the above mentioned conceptualization of the social self image congruity construct, and in line with Hair et al (2003) recommendations regarding summated scales development, the current study developed a 5 points Likert type scale to measure the social self/brand image congruity on the bases of Sirgy et al's (1997) global method and Khaldi's (2006) situation-free congruity scale development. The social self/brand image scale consisted of nine interval items as table 4 indicates.

Table 4. The global measure of the social self/brand congruence that is developed by the current study

	<i>Strongly agree</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Neither agree nor disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Strongly disagree</i>
Using XYZ Brand is not similar to how I like others to see me.*	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Others see me as the kind of person who typically uses XYZ Brand .	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
People do not see me as having much in common with the image of the XYZ Brand user.*	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
When others see me Using XYZ Brand , it makes them feel highly of me.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand completes the image of who I would like to be in front of people.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand does not reflect the kind of person I prefer others to see.*	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand helps me to express a more positive image of myself when interacting with people.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
People might like me better if I were to use XYZ Brand .	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
Using XYZ Brand would make others think I am more special than using other brands.	[]	[]	[]	[]	[]
* Reverse coded					

In order to test the validity and reliability of the new scale, a convenience sample of 461 university

students were instructed to indicate their level of agreement, or disagreement, with each item of the scale regarding a well known sunglasses brand. Respondents were also instructed to respond to a scale measuring their brand preference (adopted from Sirgy et al 1997) as a criterion variable and another scale measuring their brand attitude. The attitude scale is a modified compilation of brand attitude measures adopted from previous research (Mitchell & Olson 1981, Sheffet 1983, Batra & Ray 1986, Park et al. 2010, Lee and Koo 2015).

6. Scale Validation and Factor Analysis

The internal consistency test for the social self/brand congruence scale items produced a high Cronbach Alpha indexes of 0.897 and indicated that internal consistency cannot be significantly enhanced (for example, through deleting certain items) as table 5 indicates.

Table 5. Reliability test for the social self/brand congruence scale

Scale Item	Alpha If Item Deleted
1.	.888
2.	.911
3.	.913
4.	.872
5.	.868
6.	.872
7.	.873
8.	.881
9.	.883

Content validity of the proposed social self/brand congruity measures is already established through the conceptual basis upon which scales items were derived as discussed earlier. The criterion validity of the social self congruence measure is demonstrated by strong and significant correlations with the brand preference and brand attitudes scales respectively (Sirgy et al 1997) as table 6 indicates.

Table 6. Criterion validity correlation scores for the social self congruity scale.

Pearson Correlation	Brand Preference	Brand Attitude
Social Self Congruity	.736**	.584**
Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
N	461	461

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Regression analysis is used to demonstrate the predictive validity of the social self congruence measure (Sirgy et al 1997). The results confirm the ability of ability of the social self congruence measure to strongly and significantly predict brand preference and brand attitude respectively as table 7 indicates.

Table 7. Predictive validity regression scores for the social self congruity scale

Dependent Variable: Brand Preference					
Model R Square = 0.542	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.558	.094		5.940	.000
Social Self Congruity	.873	.037	.736	23.309	.000
Dependent Variable: Brand Attitude					
Model R Square = 0.341	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.300	.131		2.296	.022
Social Self Congruity	.804	.052	.584	15.422	.000

Exploratory factor analysis results for the social self/brand image congruence scale indicate data appropriateness for factor analysis which is demonstrated by a high value (0.903) of KMO measure of sampling adequacy index, and a significant chi square value as Table 8 shows.

Table 8. KMO and Bartlett's test for the social self congruence scale.

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.	.903
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. 2990.053
	Chi-Square
	df 36
	Sig. .000

The small values of the anti-image item correlation matrix provided another indication of the social self congruence scale data appropriateness for factor analysis, and the diagonal of the matrix provided high values for measures of sampling adequacy for each individual item as well, as Table 9 indicates.

Table 9. The anti-image matrix for the social self congruence scale

Items	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1	.949^a	-.069	-.143	-.045	.016	-.022	-.220	-.119	-.111
2	-.069	.733^a	-.325	.032	.014	-.152	.034	.067	-.070
3	-.143	-.325	.643^a	-.059	-.061	.085	.030	.034	.040
4	-.045	.032	-.059	.918^a	-.486	-.037	-.179	-.083	-.063
5	.016	.014	-.061	-.486	.874^a	-.445	-.217	-.108	-.105
6	-.022	-.152	.085	-.037	-.445	.908^a	-.301	-.007	-.061
7	-.220	.034	.030	-.179	-.217	-.301	.932^a	-.078	.050
8	-.119	.067	.034	-.083	-.108	-.007	-.078	.913^a	-.446
9	-.111	-.070	.040	-.063	-.105	-.061	.050	-.446	.909^a

Exploratory factor analysis produced a two factor solution which explained 0.71 of the social self congruence scale variance, as Table 10 indicates.

Table 10 Eigenvalues for the social self congruence factor solution

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues	% of Explained Variance	Cumulative %
1	5.170	57.446	57.446
2	1.281	14.236	71.682
3	.662	7.350	79.033
4	.591	6.568	85.601
5	.529	5.877	91.478
6	.276	3.071	94.549
7	.213	2.365	96.915
8	.179	1.990	98.905
9	.099	1.095	100.000

The suggested two factor model provided a two-item factor (only items 2 and 3 loaded on the second factor) which is not statistically recommended (Hair et al 1998, Sekaran 2003) and the rest of the items loaded on the first factor as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Exploratory factor loadings of the social self congruence scale.

Scale Items	Factor loadings	
	1	2
1	.657	.183
2	.053	.790
3	-.046	.842
4	.900	.000
5	.932	.004
6	.892	.017
7	.895	-.014
8	.843	-.100
9	.801	-.040

In order to confirm the dimensionality of the social self congruence scale, confirmatory factor analysis for two different models were conducted. The first model was a two factors solution that resembled the suggested solution of the exploratory factor analysis. The second model represented a single factor hypothesized model. Fit indexes for the two models are presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Model fit indexes for two social self congruence models.

Fit Indexes	Two Factors Model	Single Factor Model
<i>Absolute</i>		
Chi-square	26.814	2.651
Sig. value	P = 0.021	P = 0.871
GFI	0.925	0.986
RMSR	0.035	0.005
SRMR	0.042	0.012
RMSEA	0.091	0.000
<i>Incremental</i>		
AGFI	0.925	0.997
NFI	0.904	0.989
NNFI	0.961	1.089
IFI	0.911	1.047
CFI	0.926	1.084
<i>Parsimonious</i>		
AIC	7.74561	-10.95421
CAIC	-21.54781	-46.35987

The average absolute standardized residuals for the two factors model equalled 0.042 and the average for the off-diagonal absolute standardized residuals equalled 0.049 whereas for the single factor model, the average absolute standardized residuals equalled 0.006 and the average for the off-diagonal absolute standardized residuals equalled 0.010. The distribution of standardized residuals for the two factors model confined about 86% of the standardized residuals inside the range of $-0.1/+0.1$, while for the single factor model 100% of the standardized residuals were confined within that range.

The comparisons of model fit indexes between the two factors and the single factor model of the social self congruence scale indicated that although the two factors model demonstrated some acceptable fit with the data, the single factor model had far better fit especially with chi square, RMSEA, and parsimonious fit indexes. Furthermore, the single factor model produced smaller standardized residuals, and demonstrated better global fit, through the distribution of the standardized residuals, than the two factors model.

The content validity of the social self congruence scale was also demonstrated through the high values of goodness of fit indexes (Byrne 1994) that were discussed earlier. Convergent validity was demonstrated by significant item loadings ($> .30$) on the hypothesised factor (Bagozzi & Yi 1988), with high, positive, and significant parameter estimates (Anderson & Gerbing 1988) as shown in Table 13.

Table 13. Confirmatory factor loadings of the social self congruence scale

Scale Items	Factor loadings**	R ²
1	.638	.424
2	.365	.291
3	.316	.249
4	.832	.786
5	.876	.865
6	.830	.790
7	.817	.756
8	.724	.618
9	.704	.583
** ($P < 0.01$) for all loadings.		

Confirmatory factor analysis results indicate that the social self congruence scale can be considered as a valid and reliable construct as represented by SEM.

7. Conclusion

The current study proposed a global situation free measure of the social self congruity construct. The items of the construct were derived according to the conceptualisation of the previous literature in order to preserve content validity of the scale. The scale was proved to be reliable and valid through rigorous statistical procedures. Cronbach Alpha demonstrated high reliability of the proposed social self congruity measure. Criterion, predictive, and convergent validity were all demonstrated by correlation and regression analysis as well as

confirmatory factor analysis. The uni-dimensionality of the proposed construct was also proved through confirmatory factor analysis. Therefore, it can be concluded that the single factor model that was proposed by this study truly represent a valid and reliable measure of the social self congruence construct.

References

- Aaker, J. (1997) Dimensions of Brand Personality *Journal of Marketing Research* 34 (1) August pp.347-357
- Allen, D. E. and Olson, J. (1995) Conceptualizing And Creating Brand Personality: A Narrative Theory Approach *Advances in Consumer Research* Vol. 22 pp. 392-393
- Anderson, J. C. and Gerbing D. W. (1988) Structural Equation Modelling in Practice: A Review and Recommended Two-Step Approach *Psychological Bulletin* 103 (3) pp.411-423
- Assael, H. (1987) *Consumer behavior and Marketing Action* 3rd ed, Boston: Kent Publishing.
- Bagozzi, R. P. and Yi, Y. (1988) On the Evaluation of Structural Equation Models *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 16 (1) pp.74-94
- Balick, A. (2014) *The psychodynamics Of social Networking: Connected-up Instantaneous Culture and the Self.* Karnac Books Ltd
- Batra, R. and Ray M. L. (1986) Affective Responses Mediating Acceptance of Advertising *Journal of Consumer Research*, 13 (September) pp. 234-249
- Belk, R. W. (1988) Possessions and the Extended Self *Journal of Consumer Research*, 15, (September) pp.139-168
- Burroughs, J. E. (1996) Product Symbolism, Self Meaning, And Holistic Matching: The Role Of Information Processing In Impulsive Buying *Advances in Consumer Research* Volume 23. pp.463-469
- Byrne, B. (1994) *Structural Equation Modelling with EQS and EQS/windows* California: Sage Publications.
- Dobni, D. and Zinkhan, G. M. (1990) " In Search Of Brand Image: A Foundation Analysis" *Advances in Consumer Research* Volume 17.
- Fournier, S. (1995) "The Brand-As-Relationship Partner: An Alternative View Of Brand Personality" *Advances in Consumer Research* Volume 22.
- Friedman, R. (1986). 'Psychological Meaning of Products: Identification and Marketing Applications', *Psychology and Marketing*, 3 (Spring)
- Gardner, B. B. and Sidney J. Levy. (1955). "The Product and the Brand," *Harvard Business Review*. 33 (April).
- Grimm, P. E. (1993) " Determinants of Brand Preference" Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, State University Of New York At Buffalo
- Hair, J.; Anderson, R. E.; Tatham, R. L.; and Black W. C. (1998) "Multivariate Data Analysis" 5th ed., Prentice-Hall International, Inc.
- Hair, J.; Babin, B.; Money A. H.; and Samouel P. (2003) "Essentials Of Business Research Methods" Wiley
- Hood, B. (2012) *The Self Illusion: How the Social Brain Creates Identity*, Oxford University Press
- Hughes, G. D. & Naert, P. A., (1970), "A computer-controlled experiment in consumer behavior." *Journal of Business*, 43, 354-372.
- Johar, J. S. and Sirgy, M. J. (1991) "Value-Expressive Versus Utilitarian Advertising Appeals: When and Why to Use Which Appeal" *Journal of Advertising* 20
- Kang, J. (1996) "Decision-Making Processes For The Initiation Of Physical Activity: The Moderating Effects Of self-esteem And Action Control On The Relationships Among Attitudes, self-image Congruency, And Intentions To Exercise" Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, The University Of Michigan
- Kang, J. and Johnson, K (2015) Positive word-of-mouth for mobile location-based service retail apps usage, *International Journal of Mobile Communications*. Volume 13, Issue 6
- Khalidi, A. (2006), An Investigation of Self and Brand Image Congruence as Antecedents of Consumer Brand Involvement, Unpublished PhD thesis, Huddersfield University, UK
- Khalidi, A. (2014), "The Effect of Virtual Self Congruency on Consumer's Involvement in Social Media and the Motivation to Consume Social Media" *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, Volume 6, Number 1
- Kotler, P. (1988), "Marketing Management: Analysis, Planning and Control", Prentice-Hall, Englewood Cliffs, NJ.
- Lee, Y and Koo, J. (2015), Athlete Endorsement, Attitudes, and Purchase Intention: The Interaction Effect between Athlete Endorser-product Congruence and Endorser Credibility. A paper presented at The North American Society for Sport Management Conference. USA
- Levy, S. J. (1978), "Marketplace Behavior". NY:AMACOM.
- MacKinnon, N. and Heise, D. (2010) *Self, Identity, and Social Institutions*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- Maheshwari, A. D., (1974), Self-product image congruence: "A Micro-level Analysis. Ann Arbor, Michigan University Micro-film.
- Malhotra, N. (1981) "A Scale To Measure Self Concept, Person Concept, And Product Concept" *Journal Of Marketing Research*, Vol.18, November.

- Mitchell, A. and Olson J. C. (1981), "Are Product Attribute Beliefs the Only Mediator of Advertising Effects on Brand Attitude?" *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18 (August)
- Overstreet, K. L.(1993) "Children's Inferences Based On Brand Personality" Unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, University Of North Texas
- Park, C.W., MacInnis, D.J., Priester, J., Eisingreich, A.B. and Iacobucci, D. (2010), "Brand attachment and brand attitude strength", *Journal of Marketing*, Vol. 74, November
- Quester, P. G.; Karunaratna A.; and Goh L. K. (2000) "Self-Congruity And Product Evaluation: A Cross-Cultural Study" *Journal Of Consumer Marketing*, Vol I7, No. 6.
- Schenk. C. T. and Holman R. H. (1980). "A Socio-logical Approach to Brand Choice: The Concept of Situational self-image," in *Advances in Consumer Research*, Vol. 7.
- Schiffman, L., and Kanuk, L. L., (2000) "Consumer Behaviour" 7th edition, New Jersey: Prentice Hall.
- Sekaran, U. (2003) "Research Methods for Business: A Skill-Building Approach" 4th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Sheffet, M. J. (1983), "An Experimental Investigation of the Documentation of Advertising Claims," *Journal of Advertising*, 12 (1)
- Sirgy, J and Danes, J. (1981). "Self-Image/Product-Image Congruence Models: Testing Selected Mathematical Models," in *Advances in Consumer Research*. Vol. 9, ed. Andrew Mitchell. Ann Arbor: MI: Association for Consumer Research. 556-561
- Sirgy, J M.; Grewal, D.; Mangleburg, T. F.; Park, J.; Chon, K.; Claiborne, C. B.; Johar, J. S.; and Berkman, H. (1997) "Assessing the predictive validity of two methods of measuring self-image congruence" *Academy of Marketing Science*. Vol.25, Issue3.
- Sirgy, M. J. , Johar, J. S. and Wood M. (1986), "Determinants of Product Value Expressiveness: Another Look at Conspicuousness, Differentiation, and Common Usage," in *Developments in Marketing Science*, Vol. 9, ed. Naresh Malhotra, Atlanta, GA: Academy of Marketing Science
- Sirgy, M. Joseph and A. Coskun Samli (1985), "A path analytic model of store loyalty involving self-concept, store image, socioeconomic status, and geographic loyalty," *The Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 13 (Summer).
- Sirgy, M. J. (1982), "self-concept in consumer behavior: A critical review" *Journal Of Consumer Research*, Vol. 9, Dec.
- Sixt, M. (2013) *Social Media in the Tourism Industry: How Social Media and The Self Congruity Theory Affect Destination Choice*. Unpublished thesis. California Polytechnic State University.
- Smith, M. B. (1992). "William James and the psychology of self". In M. E. Donnelly (Ed), *Reinterpreting the Legacy of William James*, Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Solomon, M. R. (2002) "Consumer Behavior: Buying, Having, and Being" 5th edition, Prentice Hall International.
- To, J. (1994) "The Construction Of Image From The Perspective Of Communicators In Corporate And Government Organizations" unpublished Ph.D. Dissertation, University Of Georgia
- Tucker, W. T. (1957). "Foundations for a Theory of Consumer Behavior", New York: Holt, Rinehart & Winston.
- Wicklund, R. A. and Golwitzer P. M. (1982) "Symbolic Self-Completion" Hillsdale, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Wright, N. D., Claiborne C. B., and Sirgy, M. J. (1992) "The Effects Of Product Symbolism On Consumer Self-Concept" *Advances in Consumer Research* Volume 19